

LINGUOCULTURAL CONCEPT ABOUT HAIR

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Annotation: In this article, the concept of language and culture, general information about the concept, and a little information about the culture and values of Uzbeks through the concept of hair are presented.

Key words: linguocultural meaning, information about concept, tradition and concept of hair.

Linguocultural is a branch of linguistics that emerged at the intersection of linguistics, cultural studies, the study of the reflection and establishment of national culture in language. Linguocultural is a scientific study of the issues of language and culture, intercultural communication, because: "Language is closely connected with culture, it reaches culture, develops in it and expresses it". This field studies not only culture, but through it various national traditions, religious phenomena, national concepts, means of conscious perception of the world through language. The language map of the world generally corresponds to their logical expression in the minds of people. Wide and deep scientific study of this issue is related to linguocultural and linguocognitology.

The term concept began to appear in linguistics studies in the first half of the 20th century. This term (concept) is an English word and is equivalent to the Russian term ponyatie (concept). In later times, when the concept began to be mixed with the term, studies aimed at clearly forming its literal meaning began to be researched.

Scientists have repeatedly emphasized that the concept has a special place in cognitive linguistics. In particular, Ye.S. Kubryakova thinks that the Concept is a unit of thought that reflects our mind and mental capabilities, as well as human knowledge and experience. In his opinion, the conceptual system is a structure that reflects thinking and the image of reality in the human psyche, memory is an active content unit of the mental lexicon, the conceptual system of the brain, the whole world view is reflected in the human soul.

In the linguistic encyclopedic dictionary, this term is defined as follows: "A concept is a concept like "word meaning" that differs only from the point of view of the system of connections; the meaning is in the language system; the concept is in the system of logical relations and forms that are studied in both logic and linguistics". We can say that concept means concept and I want to express the concept of "hair". This is a very interesting topic. Girls' education and hair care have always had a special place in Uzbek families. Our grandmothers mainly dealt with this issue. It is not secret that the beautiful hair is praised in the ghazals of our classic

poets and poems of our modern artists, sung by our hafiz, and captivated by many lovers. A special place is given to the description of the hair of beauties and fairies in the epics, which are the expression of the centuries-old dreams of our people.

For example, in order to express the beauty of Zulkhumor, the hero of the "Ravshan" saga, his hair is described as follows: "...he had 95 in oil, 95 in this oil, 10 less than 200 kokili. He dipped one oil in gold water, one oil in silver water, and dried it in the morning wind...". This is undoubtedly the expression of our people's dreams about girls' hair.

Hair expresses a woman's beauty, elegance and delicacy, taste. As much as it is immoral among our people to spread hair, combing it in a public place, combing it and putting it on other people's clothes is considered indecent. I have never seen my mother wash her hair. Our grandmothers used to tell us that it would be bad if we combed our hair in a place where no one could see, and that it would be bad if our hair fell on the ground.

But today it has become a habit among girls to spread their hair. Educational institutions, public transport, kitchens - in general, we come across girls, sometimes even middle-aged women, spreading their hair in public places. This situation continues both in the cold days of winter and spring. Hair stuck on the ground, floor, kitchen appliances, underfoot, and clothes makes the mind dull.

In the last school year, schoolgirls were instructed to wear caps. On the streets, girls dressed in hats were pleasing to the eye. With the arrival of spring, this year too, you can see little girls wearing hats. But this tradition is limited only to primary classes. It is desirable to popularize this within special secondary educational institutions as well.

Our girls, who have been beautiful for thousands of years, cut their long hair, wear caps, and wrap scarves. According to Hazrat Navoi, girls with the same hair are the dream of every Uzbek boy. Therefore, first of all, we adults should pay attention to their upbringing.

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